

Synthesis and Spectral Studies on Divalent Metal Complexes of Theophylline[†]

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Theophylline complexes with metals of the type $ML_2 \cdot XH_2O$, where $M = Cu^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pt^{II} and Pd^{II} ; $HL =$ theophylline; $X = 2$ to 4 , have been synthesised and characterised from their elemental analyses, ir spectra, magnetic susceptibility and TGA data. The infrared spectra indicated that the carbonyl stretching bands of theophylline are relatively intact after complexation with the metal ions. Bonding of the theophylline anion through the imidazole nitrogen, N-7 to the metal ion is implied. The change in the magnetic properties as bis(theophyllinato) copper(II)tetrahydrate is dehydrated, implies structural rearrangement in the first coordination sphere of copper.

THE interactions of nucleic acids and nucleic acid constituents with transition-metal ions have been extensively studied^{1,2} in recent years because of the implications that interactions of this type might have for base sequencing in the genetic code. Owing to its marked biological importance, theophylline (1,3-dimethylxanthine) and other methylxanthine preparations are used in therapeutics as diuretics, cardiac stimulants, vasodilators, etc.³. Only a few crystal structure studies of copper(II) compounds containing theophylline as one of the participating ligands have been reported⁴⁻⁶. Some copper(II) compounds of the type $[(Purine)_2Cu(N)_2] \cdot XH_2O$, where purine is the deprotonated form of theophylline, N is an alkylamine, were prepared and characterised by ir spectra^{7,8}. A number of divalent metal complexes of theophylline of the type $ML_2 \cdot XH_2O$, where $M = Cu^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} ; $HL =$ theophylline; and $X = 2$ to 4 , have been synthesised in pure state and were characterised by their elemental analyses, infrared, magnetic susceptibility and TGA data. The results are presented in this communication.

Experimental

K_2PtCl_4 and K_2PdCl_4 were prepared by the reported methods⁹. Theophylline was procured from C. H. Boehringer-Sohn, Germany. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599B infrared spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature using the Faraday method with mercuric tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) employed as calibrant. The thermogravimetric and differential thermal analyses were carried out in platinum crucibles (0.3 ml capacity) in a Netzsch STA 40 thermal analyser, at the heating rate of 5° min^{-1} in static air.

(Theophyllinato)potassium monohydrate, $K(C_7H_7N_4O_2) \cdot H_2O$: Theophylline (1.8 g, 0.01 mol) was suspended in water (50 ml) and a dilute solution of KOH was added with stirring till a clear solution was obtained. It was filtered, if necessary, and evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The solid was suspended in DMF (50 ml), stirred well, filtered and washed with alcohol (5 ml portions twice) and vacuum dried (1.0 g, 43.5%), 340° d (Found: C, 35.55; H, 4.05; K, 17.23. $C_7H_7N_4O_2K$ calcd. C, 35.58; H, 3.84; K, 16.5%).

Bis(theophyllinato)copper(II) tetrahydrate, $Cu(theoph)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$: Clear solutions (filtered, if necessary) of theophylline (0.9 g, 0.005 mol) in hot water (50 ml) and copper chloride dihydrate, $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, (0.43 g, 0.0025 mol) in water (25 ml) were mixed together and the pH of the mixed solution was adjusted to 6.0 with dilute KOH solution and heated on a water-bath for 3 h. The bright bluish green solid obtained was collected on a filter under suction, washed with hot water and dried (0.9 g, 72%), 200° d (Found: C, 33.37; H, 5.03; N, 22.2; Cu, 12.72. $C_{14}H_{14}N_8O_8Cu$ calcd. C, 34.04; H, 4.49; N, 22.7; Cu, 12.86%); μ_{eff} 1.78 B.M.

Bis(theophyllinato)copper(II), $Cu(theoph)_2$: The anhydrous copper complex was obtained by drying the tetrahydrate at $170-175^\circ$ for about 5 h. The complex is diamagnetic (Found: C, 40.51; H, 4.01; N, 25.2; Cu, 15.10. $C_{14}H_{14}N_8O_4Cu$ calcd. C, 39.86; H, 3.34; N, 26.57; Cu, 15.07%).

Hydrated Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes were prepared essentially in the above manner except that triethylamine (~ 7 ml) in alcohol (15 ml) was added to the mixed solutions (Ni and Co) and was heated on a water-bath for 4-5 h. In case of cadmium complex, dilute aqueous ammonia solution was added till the precipitate first formed was redissolved and the mixture heated on a water-bath.

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Bis(theophyllinato)nickel(II)tetrahydrate, $Ni(\text{theoph})_2 \cdot 4H_2O$: The compound reveals m.p. $>300^\circ d$ (Found: C, 34.70; H, 5.35, N, 23.3; Ni , 11.61. $C_{14}H_{22}N_8O_8Ni$ calcd. C, 34.38; H, 4.53; N, 22.92; Ni , 12.00%); μ_{eff} 2.29 B.M.

Bis(theophyllinato)cobalt(II)tetrahydrate, $Co(\text{theoph})_2 \cdot 4H_2O$: The compound reveals m.p. $>300^\circ d$ (Found: C, 35.07; H, 4.77; N, 23.27; Co , 12.6. $C_{14}H_{22}N_8O_8Co$ calcd. C, 34.36; H, 4.53; N, 22.91; Co , 12.04%); μ_{eff} 4.70 B.M.

Bis(theophyllinato)cadmium(II)trihydrate, $Cd(\text{theoph})_2 \cdot 3H_2O$: The compound reveals m.p. $300^\circ d$ (Found: C, 32.81; H, 4.06; N, 20.78; Cd , 20.69. $C_{14}H_{20}N_8O_7Cd$ calcd. C, 32.04; H, 3.84; N, 21.35; Cd , 21.41%).

Mn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes were prepared by mixing clear solutions of theophylline in dilute KOH solution and the corresponding metal salt in water or alcohol in 2:1 mole ratio and heating the mixture for 5-6 h on a water-bath. The solid products obtained were collected on a filter under suction, washed with hot water and dried.

Bis(theophyllinato)manganese(II)tetrahydrate, $Mn(\text{theoph})_2 \cdot 4H_2O$: The compound reveals m.p. $>300^\circ d$ (Found: C, 34.61; H, 5.3; N, 22.8; Mn , 11.75. $C_{14}H_{22}N_8O_8Mn$ calcd. C, 34.64; H, 4.57; N, 23.10; Mn , 11.32%); μ_{eff} 6.21 B.M.

Bis(theophyllinato)mercury(II)dihydrate, $Hg(\text{theoph})_2 \cdot 2H_2O$: The compound reveals m.p. $280^\circ d$ (Found: Hg , 34.14; N, 17.55. $C_{14}H_{18}N_8O_6Hg$ calcd. Hg , 33.71; N, 18.84%).

Bis(theophyllinato)palladium(II)trihydrate, $Pd(\text{theoph})_2 \cdot 3H_2O$: The compound reveals m.p. 260 d (Found: C, 31.57; H, 4.07; N, 19.85; Pd , 20.59. $C_{14}H_{20}N_8O_7Pd$ calcd. C, 32.39; H, 3.88; N, 21.59; Pd , 20.56%).

Bis(theophyllinato)platinum(II)tetrahydrate, $Pt(\text{theoph})_2 \cdot 4H_2O$: The compound reveals m.p. $300^\circ d$ (Found: C, 25.93; H, 3.50; N, 16.82; Pt , 32.00. $C_{14}H_{22}N_8O_8Pt$ calcd. C, 26.87; H, 3.54; N, 17.92; Pt , 31.20%).

Results and Discussion

The infrared spectra of all the metal complexes exhibit similarities to each other and consistent variation from the spectrum of theophylline. In the ir spectrum of theophylline, two distinct peaks in the 1600-1800 region, one at 1720 and the other at 1680 cm^{-1} , attributable to C=O stretching vibration^{10,11} were observed. On complexation these bands maintained similar patterns with slight widening and shifted to 1690 and 1650 cm^{-1} suggesting the absence of interaction of the carbonyl group with the metal ion. In the region $2500\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the spectrum of theophylline shows complex absorption pattern. The NH band could be located at $ca\ 3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$. However, a strong band at 2610 cm^{-1} was observed, a wavelength much longer than usually associated with C-H stretching motion. In free

theophylline, the oxygen atom at C-6 is believed to be hydrogen bonded to the imino-hydrogen at N-7¹². On complexation the broad bands in the region $2500\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the theophylline spectrum largely disappeared or weakened. Bands observed in the region $1555\text{--}1590\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to C=C stretching vibrations. The intensities of the absorption bands observed in the region $1555\text{--}1590\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of complexes, are somewhat stronger than for pure theophylline. This is accounted for by the modification in the energy of the C=N bond of the purine cycle upon coordination¹³. As there is no tautomeric form for theophylline due to the methyl group at N-1, the hydrogen atom replaced could not be derived from the enol group at C-6. The proton released is very likely the hydrogen atom at N-7. This is reflected by the changes in the infrared spectra after complexation of theophylline with metal ions in the region $2500\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The spectra of all the complexes show slight attenuation of the free theophylline^{13,14} (940 and 950 cm^{-1}) bands as well as small shift of the band maximum in the $1200\text{--}1210\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range. The complexes reported herein contain theophylline anion bound to the metal through the imidazole nitrogen, N-7. Theophylline anion is bound to metal through N-7 in most of the reported metal ion theophylline complexes and various other ligands attached to the central metal^{7,8}. In fact, the anion does not seem to act as chelate in many complexes whose structures have been determined⁶. Recently a new mode of theophylline anion metal bonding, a trimeric complex with trimethyl platinum(IV) which contains Pt-N(7)-N(9)-Pt bridges and a weak direct (C-6)-O-Pt bond has, however, been reported by Hall *et al.*¹⁵. The ir spectra of all the complexes show broad absorptions in the $3350\text{--}3450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region consistent with the presence of water molecules. In the spectrum of anhydrous bis(theophyllinato)copper(II), this broad band disappeared.

Thermal analysis of theophylline complexes of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Mn^{II} was carried out in air. Bis(theophyllinato)copper(II)tetrahydrate lost the bonded water in the temperature region $84\text{--}182^\circ$ and accelerated weight loss occurred in the range $350\text{--}480^\circ$. Complete loss of water of hydration occurred at 182° (Found: 14.6% . $4H_2O$ calcd. 14.57%). For the manganese complex the loss occurred at 195° (Found: 14.95% . $4H_2O$ calcd. 14.84%). DTA curves show endothermic peaks corresponding to these temperatures. Loss of water of hydration for the Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes occurred at $115\text{--}200^\circ$ and at 180° , and accelerated weight loss in the temperature region $375\text{--}475^\circ$ and at $350\text{--}560^\circ$, respectively.

The hydrated metal-theophylline complexes (Ni - Co , Mn) showed expected magnetic moments. However, a drastic change in magnetic behaviour is observed as the bis(theophyllinato)copper(II)tetrahydrate (μ_{eff} 1.78 B.M.) is dehydrated - the anhydrous copper(II) complex is diamagnetic. Melnik¹⁶ has recently reported the isolation of bis(theophyllinato)-copper(II)dihydrate and observed similar magnetic

behaviour for the anhydrous copper complex. The behaviour is interpreted in terms of antiferromagnetically exchange-coupled pairs of copper atoms. The change in magnetic properties implies that structural rearrangement in first coordination sphere of copper accompanies the dehydration process.

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